

Impact of Staff Training on Teachers' Job Performance in Primary Schools in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State

Joy Idowu Chiakyor¹, Eunice Mwuese Agba² and Ruth Mbakaren Tor-Anyin³

¹Department of Preprimary Social Studies Education, Joseph Sarwuan Tarka University, Makurdi, Nigeria.

^{2,3}Department of Arts and Social Sciences Education, Benue State University, Makurdi, Nigeria.

Received 17 January 2025; Acceptance 25 February 2025; Published 18 March 2025.

Abstract

The study investigated the impact of staff training on teachers' job performance in primary schools in Makurdi local government area of Benue State. Three research questions were raised and answered and three hypotheses were formulated and tested. Survey research design was adopted for this study. A sample of 200 respondents comprising teachers from twenty primary schools was selected using random sampling technique to respond to the questionnaire. A structured questionnaire titled "Impact of Teachers Training on Job Performance Questionnaire (ITTJPQ)" was used for data collection. The data collected were analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer research questions while chi-square was used to test the hypotheses at 0.5 level of significance. From the data analysis, the following findings were obtained; There is a significant impact of teachers' training on academic performance of pupils in public primary schools in Makurdi local government area. There is a significant impact of teachers' training on instructional delivery in the classroom in public primary schools in Makurdi local government area. There is a significant impact of teachers' training on implementation of curriculum in public primary schools in Makurdi local government area. Based on the findings it is concluded that teachers training has significant impact on teachers' job performance in terms of students' academic performance, classroom instructional delivery and curriculum implementation in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State. It was recommended that Benue State Universal Basic Education Board (SUBEB) should regularly organized training workshops for primary school teachers.

Keywords: Staff training, Teachers, Job performance, Primary school.

Introduction

Education is the key to civilization and national development and teachers hold the key to civilization and national development as no nation can be great or rise above the quality of its educational system and no educational system can rise above the quality of its teachers. The success of an educational system

Correspondence to: Joy Idowu Chiakyor, e-mail: joyidowu7@gmail.com

Copyright: © 2025 The authors. This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License.

How to Cite: Chiakyor et al. (2025). Impact of Staff Training on Teachers Job Performance in Primary Schools in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State. *Scholar J - Science and Education*, 3(3). DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15046035

depends largely on the performance of teachers, who can be considered as the backbone of the system (Amin, Shah, Ayaz, & Atta, 2013). The performance of teachers largely depend on training. Training can be described as a systematic way of stimulating efficiency and high performance through learning processes. Perraton (2007) refers to teacher training as the policies, procedures, and provision designed to equip teachers with the knowledge, attitudes, behaviors, and skills they require to perform their tasks effectively in the classroom, school, and wider community. Training connotes a planned process to modify attitudes so as to achieve effective performance in a range of activities. It can further be described as an organized procedure which is based on individual needs for satisfying specific job requirements. It is therefore, a necessary exercise carried out to give a staff the needed and required knowledge or skills: its aim is to solve particular organizational problems.

According to Ojiemhenkele (2014) teacher training refers to any support and capacity building which enables teachers and other education personnel to effectively instruct and assess learners on the curricula. Teacher development programs are based on actual and evolving needs of both teachers and learners. There should be a clear link between the curriculum, learning rights, needs of students and their families, and teacher training and continued teacher support. Teachers and other education personnel should receive periodic, relevant, and structured training according to needs and circumstances. Pre-service training refers to the training teachers receive before entering a classroom and beginning to teach. In-service training refers to the continued training opportunities given to teachers after they have begun teaching in classrooms.

Adeleke, (2000) observed that teachers' competence on the job is acquired not only by formal education but also through the acquisition of specific skills and knowledge on the job by training and development. Greater emphasis should therefore be placed on training and development as a panacea for obtaining competent teachers for the educational system. Christhi and Ajmal (2011) affirm that regular training programmes for teachers provide them with the necessary job knowledge, skills, ability and competency that is relevant for a smooth career of a teacher. Further, they added that the personality of the teachers is reshaped, their attitudes are properly shaped, their working habits are reformed and their personality is built only through training programme which could also impact on the academic performance of the students.

The ability of schools to continue their operations and achieve their goals depends largely on teachers' job performance. Teachers job performance is simply defined as all behaviours in which teachers engage at work or as measurable actions, behaviours and outputs directly engaged in or indirectly caused by teachers to serve school objectives (Viswesvaran & Ones, 2000). In another definition Motowidlo (2003) states that teachers job performance is the expected total value of behavioural episodes displayed by the teachers at a given period. According to Jamal (2007) job performance can be defined as the extent to which an employee can carry out the tasks successfully using the school resources under regular conditions. As can be understood from the definitions, job performance can be understood in terms of teachers' behaviour or outcomes produced by the teachers.

For any educational system to invest in training and development programmes for her teachers implies toeing a right direction in the realization of the educational goals of the society as this will go a long way in enhancing the performance of the teachers in their jobs which could improve students' academic performance. The quality of teachers that work in a specific educational system help in the attainment of positive learning outcomes in schools. Performance of teachers is partly dependent on their preserve training in addition to the in-service training given to the teachers. Pre-service teacher training programs (PSTP) are very crucial in order to upgrade teachers' skills, knowledge and performance and also to enable them to be more effective in classroom instructional delivery.

On the other hand, In-service training programs (ISTP) are necessary to re-orientate teachers to new goals and values, to train them in new teaching and learning methods, new instructional materials, to prepare them to cope with curriculum change and to provide them with the knowledge and skills to teach new learning areas (Al-Zoubi, 2010). When teachers are trained in these areas it go a long way in improving the academic performance of students. This is because the teachers are trained in innovative teaching strategies and teaching materials which they could use to captivate students' attention which will result to better students' academic performance. According to Pynes (2008) training programme seeks to change the skills, proficiency, job knowledge, or attitudes of teachers. The training programme may be focused on improving teachers' job performance through self-awareness and competency building. It can be used to expertise in one or more areas. Training and development increases teachers' motivation to perform their job well. Ojiemhenkele (2014) pointed the functions of in service training to cover: increased productivity and performance, enhancement in work quality, improved skills, knowledge, better understanding and development of positive attitudes. Appiah (2012) pointed out that training of teachers enhance knowledge for job, skills, new techniques, attributes and competencies.

The importance of training in enhancing the effectiveness of teachers in the classroom cannot be over-emphasized. This arises from the fact that it forms an integral part of the process of total quality management and enables teachers to perform their duties and responsibilities effectively so as to enable the school achieve its set goals and objectives which among others is to trained students and ensure high quality academic performance of their students. Training is thus geared towards the acquisition of specific skills or knowledge in instructional delivery in the classroom and such skills and knowledge acquired must be channel towards improved classroom instructional delivery (Appiah, 2012).

Curriculum keep changing with the needs, demands and aspirations of the society, therefore teachers must be regularly training to fit into the changes in the curriculum. Tanner and Tanner in Utulu (2011) defined curriculum as the planned and guided learning experiences and intended learning outcomes, formulated through the systematic reconstruction of knowledge and experiences under the auspices of the school for the learner's continuous and wilful growth in personal-social competences. Gbamanja (2002) considers the term curriculum as the totality of experiences which the school offers to students. These experiences according to Gbamanja should be systematically planned so as to produce positive behavioural changes in students to make them useful to themselves and the society at large. Traditionally, curriculum has been regarded as a document circulated to all teachers in an area or nation for implementation in schools (Olorundare, 2000). The curriculum is always in every society, a reflection of what the people need, their problems, believe and aspirations. Without adequate training teachers cannot implement effectively the new changes in the curriculum.

In recent years, State Universal Basic Education Board has shifted focus in providing in-service training to teachers, especially the primary schools teacher, to rather providing infrastructure, failing to recognize that this infrastructure is useless without the availability of competent trained teachers to use this educational infrastructure. Despite the efforts made by the government through the SUBEB to provide infrastructure in schools and train teachers on implementing the new 9-year basic education curriculum, teachers' job performance is still not up to the required level of performance since pupils are still performing poorly. This could be that teachers are not receiving the required in-service training. Teachers need in-service training to effectively implement changes in curriculum. It is therefore imperative to investigate the impact of staff training on teachers' job performance in primary schools in Makurdi local government area of Benue State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided this study.

1. What is the impact of teachers' training on academic performance of students in public primary schools in Makurdi local government area?
2. What is the impact of teachers' training on instructional delivery in the classroom in public primary schools in Makurdi local government area?
3. What is the impact of teachers' training on implementation of curriculum in public primary schools in Makurdi local government area?

Research Hypotheses

The following research questions were formulated and tested.

- Ho₁. There is no significant impact of teachers' training on academic performance of pupils in public primary schools in Makurdi local government area.
- Ho₂. There is no significant impact of teachers' training on instructional delivery in the classroom in public primary schools in Makurdi local government area.
- Ho₃. There is no significant impact of teachers' training on implementation of curriculum in public primary schools in Makurdi local government area.

Research Method

The research design adopted for this study was the survey design. The area of the study in this research was Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State. The population for the study comprised of all the 858 teachers in public primary schools in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State. The sample of 200 respondents were random selected from 20 primary schools. In each of the 20 sampled schools, 10 teachers were randomly selected to respond to the questionnaire. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire titled "Impact of Teachers' Training on Job Performance Questionnaire (ITTJPQ)". The instrument has a reliability coefficient of 0.87. The face to face method was used in the distribution of copies of questionnaire. The questionnaire was administered on teachers in their schools. To avoid missing copies of the questionnaire, the questionnaire was administered to the respondents and collected by the researcher within same day. Descriptive statistics of means (\bar{x}) and standard deviations (δ) were used to answer the research questions while inferential statistic of chi-square (χ^2) was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. For the research questions, cut-off point of 2.50 will be used for decision-making arising from the analysis. The decision rule was that null hypotheses were rejected if the calculated value was less than or equal to the critical or table value and not rejected if otherwise.

Results and Discussion

Results are presented according to the research questions and hypotheses.

Research Question 1: What is the impact of teachers' training on academic performance of students in public primary schools in Makurdi local government area?

Table 1. Impact of Teachers' Training on Students' Academic Performance.

S/N	Item Description	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{X}	Std. D.	Decision
1	Students taught by trained teachers attain higher academic performance than students taught by untrained teachers.	92	57	32	19	3.11	1.00	Agreed
2	Trained teachers are more knowledgeable with curriculum contents which impact positively on students' academic performance.	79	61	40	20	3.38	1.17	Agreed
3	Trained teachers are more skillful in pedagogies which could enhance students' academic performance.	91	62	30	17	3.14	1.01	Agreed
4	Trained teachers more skillful in the use of instructional materials which could enhance students' academic performance.	90	59	32	19	3.10	1.00	Agreed
Cluster mean							3.18	Agreed

Result in Table 1 shows that the respondents rated all the items in a cluster mean of 3.18 which is above the cut-off point of 2.50. This indicated that the respondents agreed with all the items. The interpretation is that teachers training enhance students' academic performance in primary schools in Makurdi LGA.

Research Question 2: What is the impact of teachers' training on instructional delivery in the classroom in public primary schools in Makurdi local government area?

Table 2. Impact of Teachers' Training on Instructional Delivery in the Classroom

S/N	Item Description	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{X}	Std. Dev.	Decision
5	Training enable teachers to acquired skills to effectively manage students in the classroom.	50	68	50	32	2.68	1.00	Agreed
6	Training help teachers to learn about new classroom teaching strategies.	92	57	20	19	2.99	1.07	Agreed
7	Training enable teachers to use different instructional strategies new	63	44	45	48	3.20	1.01	Agreed

	ways to help them improve their academic performance.							
8	Through training teachers are able to use instructional materials effectively	91	62	30	17	3.14	1.01	Agreed
Cluster mean						3.00		Agreed

Result in Table 2 shows that the respondents rated all the items with mean above the cut-off mark of 2.50 and a cluster mean of 3.00. This indicated that the respondents agreed with all the items. The interpretation is that the respondents agreed that teachers' training impact positively on their classroom instructional delivery in areas such as new teaching strategies, classroom management techniques and use of instructional materials students' academic.

Research Question 3: What is the impact of teachers' training on implementation of curriculum in public primary schools in Makurdi local government area?

Table 3. Impact of Teacher Training on Implementation of Curriculum

S/N	Item Description	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{X}	Std.D	Decision
9	Training enable teachers to adapt quickly to changes in curriculum	70	80	20	30	3.65	1.12	Agreed
10	Training help teachers to adapt different teaching strategies to suit the changes in the curriculum.	60	86	41	13	2.96	1.01	Agreed
11	Training enable teachers to be aware of curriculum content and how to teach the content in the classroom.	92	57	32	19	3.11	1.00	Agreed
12	Teachers training ensure awareness of the kind of instructional materials to use in implementing the curriculum	79	61	40	20	3.98	1.17	Agreed
Cluster mean						3.42		

Result in Table 3 shows that the respondents rated all the items in a cluster mean of 3.42 which is above the cut-off point of 2.50, this indicated that the respondents agreed with all the items. The interpretation is that teacher's training impact positively on the curriculum implementation in primary schools.

Hypotheses 1

There is no significant impact of teachers' training on academic performance of pupils in in public primary schools in Makurdi local government area.

Table 4. Chi-square Value of the impact of teachers' training on students' academic performance

Response	Fo	Fe	df	level of Sign.	X²cal.	X²Tab.	Decision
SA	84	50	4	0.05	12.00	13.42	Rejected
A	68	50					
D	30	50					
SD	18	50					

Result in Table 4 showed that chi-square calculated value of 12.00 is less than the chi-square tabulated value of 13.42 checked at 0.05 alpha level of significance and at 4 degrees of freedom. Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant impact of teachers' training on academic performance of pupils in in public primary schools in Makurdi local government area is rejected. This means that teachers' training has impact on academic performance of secondary school students.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant impact of teachers' training on instructional delivery in the classroom in public primary schools in Makurdi local government area.

Table 5. Chi-square value of impact of teachers' training on instructional delivery in the classroom

Response	Fo	Fe	Df	Sign. Level	X² Cal.	X² Tab.	Decision
SA	88	50	4	0.05	13.50	16.54	Rejected
A	64	50					
D	28	50					
SD	20	50					

Result in Table 5 indicated that the chi-square calculated value of 13.50 is less than the tabulated value of 16.54 checked at 0.05 alpha level of significance and at 4 degrees of freedom. Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant impact of teachers' training on instructional delivery in the classroom in public primary schools in Makurdi local government area is rejected. This means that teachers' training has positive impact on instructional delivery in the classroom.

Hypothesis 3

There is no significant impact of teachers' training on implementation of curriculum in public primary schools in Makurdi local government area.

Table 6. Chi-square Value of the mean responses of the impact of teachers' training on curriculum implementation

Response	Fo	Fe	Df	Sign.	X ² Cal.	X ² Tab.	Decision
SA	61	50	4	0.05	9.5	12.25	Rejected
A	80	50					
D	43	50					
SD	16	50					

Result in Table 6 indicates that the chi-square calculated value of 9.50 is less than the tabulated value of 12.25 checked at 0.05 alpha level of significance and at 4 degrees of freedom. Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant impact of teachers' training on implementation of curriculum in public primary schools in Makurdi local government area is rejected. This means that teachers' training has positive impact on curriculum implementation.

Discussion of Findings

The first finding of this study was that teachers' training has a significant impact on students' academic performance of primary school pupils in Makurdi LGA. The finding corroborates the findings of Gbodi and Dantani (2009); Udo, Uyoata, Inyon and Ekanem (2011) who found that students taught by trained teachers performed higher than those taught by untrained teachers. This also affirms the claim by Ibrahim (2010) that teachers who underwent in-service training produce students with higher performance. This is because teachers who have more training produce students who have the better academic performance.

The second finding was that teachers' training has significant impact on instructional delivery in the classroom in public primary schools in Makurdi local government area. This finding agreed with that of Ofeimu and Oluwatoyin (2017) who also found that teacher's training has significant impact on classroom instructional delivery. This finding is possible because in-service training equips teachers with skills necessary for handling multiple children with different learning needs. Training also builds the capacity of teachers on new teaching strategies. Different individual students and age groups will express various difficulties when it comes to interacting, communicating, and teaching. By being trained, a teacher will be more willing to understand each of these individual students and overall age groups. Good teaching comes with experience, however, having in-service training will allow the teacher to learn and better understand what specific tactics work and do not work when it comes to engaging students within the learning process. Being trained help teachers to be patient with students and allow them time to develop, thereby enhancing their academic performance. A trained teacher never gives up on students and would try out new ways to help them succeed in school. Some students

can comprehend the subject matter with minimal effort, while others may require more extensive explanations that may have to be repeated a number of times.

The third finding of this study was that teachers' training has significant impact on implementation of curriculum in public primary schools in Makurdi local government area. This finding agreed with that of Collie and Martin (2015) and Corno (2008) who also found that teachers training has significant impact on curriculum implementation. This finding is possible because teachers must respond to the different and changing needs of the curriculum and this is only possible if the teachers are trained. Teachers training is one the most important aspect of curriculum implementation. When a new curriculum is developed, there is always the need to trained teachers on the implementation of the curriculum. Teachers must be trained in order to cope with unexpected situations in classroom implementation of the curriculum.

Conclusion

The study concludes that teachers training has significant impact on teachers' job performance in terms of students' academic performance, classroom instructional delivery and curriculum implementation in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State. In view of the findings, it was therefore recommended among others that the Benue State Universal Basic Education Board (SUBEB) should regularly organized training workshops for primary school teachers. Training of in-service teachers should be used to correct the poor performance of pupils in primary schools. Additionally, any time that a new curriculum is to be implemented, teachers' training should be the first step to be taken to ensure successful implementation of the curriculum.

References

- Adaramola, M.O. & Obomanu, B.J. (2011). Factors related to under achievement in science, technology and mathematics education (STME) in Secondary Schools in Rivers State, Nigeria. *World Journal of Education*, 1(1), 102-109.
- Adeleke, P. (2000). Job satisfaction and commitment among university staff. Unpublished Ph.D. Thesis, University of Ibadan, Ibadan, Nigeria.
- Adeniyi, O.1. (2015). Staff training and development in Ejiogun, A; Achumba, I. Asika (eds). *Reading in Organizational Behaviour in Nigeria*. Lagos. Malthouse Press Ltd, P. 159-167.
- Adeyemi, B. (2010). Impact of teachers training on academic performance of secondary school students in Port Harcourt Rivers State Nigeria. *Electronic Journal. of Research in Educational Psychology*, 8(1), 313-332.
- Aduwa, S.E. (2014). Dynamising the instructional system: An inquiry for effective childhood education in Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Curriculum Studies*, 11(2), 239-245.
- Amin, A. A., Shah, H., Ayaz, A. M.& Atta, O. M. (2013). Teacher education in Nigeria; Trends, issues and challenges. *Nigeria Education Research Association* p.11- 15.
- Agbo, A.A. (2017). Effect of school type and the job performance of secondary schools teachers in Cross River State of Nigeria. *Journal of Educational System Development*, 5(1), 1-10.
- Agharuwhe, A. A. (2013). Effects of Teachers' Effectiveness on Students' Academic Performance in Public Secondary Schools; Delta State, Nigeria, *Journal of Educational and Social Research*,

3(3), 105-111.

Akindutire, I.O. & Ekundayo, H.T.(2012). Teacher education in a democratic Nigeria: Challenges and the way forward. *Educational Research*, 3(5), 429-435.

Akinfe, E., Olofinniyi, O. E, & Fashiku, C. O. (2012). Teachers' quality as correlates of students' academic performance in Biology in senior secondary schools in Ondo State, Nigeria. *Journal of Education Research*, 1 (6).

Akinyele, S.T. (2005). The impact of training programme on employees. *Journal of Management Enterprise Development*, 3, 24-33.

Akiri, A.A. (2013). Effects of teachers' effectiveness on students' academic performance in public secondary schools in Delta State, Nigeria. *Journal of Educational and Social Research*, 3(3), 105-112.

Al-Otaibi, S. (2015). Training needs for teaching staff members, effective teaching skills, faculty of Science, Princess Noura University. *International Educational Journal*, 12(6), 170-186.

Anao, A.R., (2013). What is training and development? Nigerian Management Reviews *Journal of Center Management Development*, 8, 24-33.

Christhi, M.H & Ajmal, G. (2011). Teachers and students' academic performance in Nigerian secondary schools: Implications for planning. *Florida Journal of Educational Administration & Planning*, 3(2), 86-103.

Collie, R.J, & Martin, A.J. (2016). Adaptability: An important capacity for effective teachers. *Educational Practice and Theory*, 38(1), 27-39.

Colombo, E. & Stanca, L. (2008). The impact of training on productivity: Evidence from a Large Panel of Firms. *Journal of Center Management Development*, 8, 34-39.

Cullen, K., Edwards, B., Casper, W. C., & Gue, K. (2014). Employees' adaptability and perceptions of change-related uncertainty: Implications for perceived organizational support, job satisfaction, and performance. *Journal of Business and Psychology*, 29(2), 269-280.

Darling-Hammond, L., Berry, B.,& Thoreson, A. (2011). Does teacher certification matter? Evaluating the evidence. *Educational Evaluation and Policy Analysis*, 23(1), 57-77.

Duncan, A. (2010). Teacher preparation: Reforming the uncertain profession. *The Education Digest*, 13-22.

Hafeez, M. (2021). Impact of Teacher's Training on Interest and Academic Achievements of Students by Multiple Teaching Methods. *Pedagogical Research*, 6(3), 213-219.

Hollins, E.R. (2011). Teacher preparation for quality teaching. *Journal of Teacher Education*, 62(4), 395-407.

- Ibrahim, A. (2010). Evaluating the pedagogical competence of junior secondary school Integrated Science teachers. *40th STAN Annual Conference Proceedings*. 138-142.
- Khan, S., & Abdullah, N. N. (2019). The impact of staff training and development on teachers' productivity. *Economics, Management and Sustainability*, 4(1), 37-45.
- Marie F. H. (2010). What makes a good teacher?' SABES/World Education, Volume 12 Boston, MA.
- Martin, A. J. (2013). Academic buoyancy and academic resilience: Exploring 'everyday' and 'classic' resilience in the face of academic adversity. *School Psychology International*, 34(5), 488-500.
- Oancea, Alis (2014). Teachers' professional knowledge and state-funded teacher education: a history of critiques and silences. *Oxford Review of Education*, 40 (4): 497–519.
- Ojiemhenkele, A. E. (2014). In-Service Training: A Panacea for Teachers' Job Effectiveness and Productivity. *Studies in Education*, 14(1).
- Olanipekun, S.S. & Aina, J.K. (2014). Improving students' academic performance in Nigerian schools: the role of teachers. *International Journal of Research in Humanities and Social Sciences*, 1(2), 1-6.
- Perraton, H. (2007). *Teacher Education: The Role of Open and Distance Learning*, London: Routledge.
- Perraton, H., Creed, C. and Robinson, B. (2002) *Teacher education guidelines: Using open and distance learning*, Paris: UNESCO.
- Stone, R. (1961). *Input-Output and National Accounts*. Paris: Organization for European Economic Co-operation.
- UNESCO. (2002). *Teacher education guidelines: using open and distance learning – technology, curriculum, cost, evaluation*. Paris: UNESCO.
- Vaughn, M., & Parsons, S. A. (2013). Adaptive teachers as innovators: Instructional adaptations opening spaces for enhanced literacy learning. *Language Arts*, 91(2), 81-93.
- Wilson, (2011). *Teacher Preparation Research: Current Knowledge, Gaps, and Recommendations*. Center for the Study of Teaching and Policy, Michigan State University.
- Zuzovsky, R. (2009). Teachers' qualifications and their impact on students' achievement findings from TIMMS-2003 data in Israel. *Issues and Methodologies in large scale Assessment*, 2, 37-62.

Publisher's Note Scholar J remains neutral with regard to jurisdictional claims in published maps and institutional affiliations.